

Corn Bioethanol Side Streams: A Potential Sustainable Source of Fat-Soluble Bioactive Molecules for High-Value Applications

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Figure S1. Relative distribution of phytosterols in post-fermentation corn oil and thin stillage from a dry-grind corn ethanol plant. Data refer to mean values obtained after saponification of 11 lots of corn oil and 7 lots of thin stillage collected at monthly intervals from June 2018 to September 2019. Legend: ERG ergosterol, AVN Δ^5 -avenasterol, STG+CAMP stigmasterol + campesterol, β -SITO β -sitosterol, STN sitostanol.

Figure S2. Relative distribution of tocopherols (T) and tocotrienols (T3) in post-fermentation corn oil and thin stillage from a dry-grind corn ethanol plant. Data refer to mean values obtained after saponification of 11 lots of corn oil and 7 lots of thin stillage collected at monthly intervals from June 2018 to September 2019.

*may contain low or trace amounts of β -homologue